

Design and Analysis of a Novel Electro-Optical MEMS Gyroscope for Navigation Applications

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Abstract – A novel gyroscope design is presented that has potential to reach navigation-grade performance, i.e. bias instability < 0.01 °/hr and Angle Random Walk (ARW) < 0.001 °/√hr. The design is based on the incorporation of an optical transduction mechanism used to decouple drive and sense signals, a dual crystalline silicon spring fabrication approach along with a large drive mass and small sense mass to enhance Coriolis displacement.

I. INTRODUCTION

Although there has been much interest in the development of a navigation-grade MEMS-based gyroscope none so far has been able to deliver on the promise of a small, low-cost alternative to macro-scale ring laser gyro (RLG) and fiber optic gyro (FOG) approaches. A large number of current MEMS gyroscope designs are based on capacitive drive and sense electrodes whereby the drive and sense resonant frequencies are closely matched [1,2]. The matching of the drive and sense resonant frequencies along with methods to increase the mechanical Q of both drive and sense axis act to increase the sense-axis coupling to the Coriolis force thereby allowing for smaller angular resolution. The increased coupling of drive and sense-axis, however, also acts to increase capacitive cross-talk which can in turn impact the angular resolution and bias instability of the design. Also, as can be seen in equation (1), the rotational bias due to cross-talk, Ω_{bias} , decreases with mechanical quality factor of the Coriolis drive, Q_c . For this reason, among others,

very large Q is often desired but at the expense of increased pressure and temperature sensitivities.

$$\Omega_{bias} = \frac{1}{2Q_c} \frac{G_c V_{xtalk}(\omega_c = \omega_d)}{x_d v_c} \omega_c \quad (1)$$

The electro-optical design described herein adopts a low Q approach. This can be achieved due to the elimination of the capacitive cross-talk signal as well as increased mechanical displacement sensitivity afforded by the optical interferometric approach.

II. FABRICATION

The fabrication of the optical gyroscope closely follows the same fabrication process flow currently used to fabricate accelerometers using the same optical transduction technique. The entire sensor assembly consists of a three wafer stack including a lower mirror wafer, proof mass wafer and bonding cap wafer. An optical Fabry-Perot cavity is formed between mirrors deposited on the bottom side of the proof mass wafer and the top side of the lower mirror wafer. Illumination of the optical cavity is done by removing the silicon inertial mass directly above the optical cavity as shown in Fig 1 and 2. This allows for direct illumination using a near IR, 850 nm, optical source.

For the purposes of this paper the most interesting aspect of the sensor assembly is the fabrication of the proof mass itself which consists of a set of upper and lower crystalline silicon springs with a silicon inertial

mass centered between the set of springs. Each spring is 30 microns thick while the inertial mass is 400 microns thick.

To optimize mechanical sensitivity of the sensor, the mass of the Coriolis drive, m_d , is mechanically decoupled from the mass in the sense direction, m_s . As will be discussed later, decoupling the drive and sense axis acts as a force multiplier acting on the sense mass thereby increasing displacement due to the Coriolis force. A top down view and cross-sectional view of the gyroscope design is shown in Fig 1 and Fig 2 respectively. It can be seen in both Fig 1 and 2 that the sense mass contains viscous damping holes that act to not only reduce the sense-axis mass but also decrease squeeze film damping thereby increasing sense-axis quality factor, Q_s . Fig 3 is an SEM micrograph showing a portion of a previously fabricated accelerometer using the same fabrication process. In this case, the accelerometer proof mass is substantially similar to the gyroscope sense mass. To fabricate the gyroscope, a drive mass can be incorporated using the same processing steps used to define the sense mass without the need for any additional masking steps. This allows for the potential future integration of two orthogonal gyroscopes and a vertical axis accelerometer to be co-integrated on the same silicon die.

Fig 1. Top-down view of the gyroscope assembly. The assembly includes a sense mass decoupled from the drive mass, dual crystalline silicon springs (upper and lower), a dual set of comb drives, mechanical stops in the lateral directions, and viscous damping holes in the sense mass to reduce viscous damping.

Fig 2. Cross-sectional cut away view of the gyroscopic assembly. The sense and drive masses include upper and lower crystalline silicon springs.

The sense-axis mass is designed to be stiff in the lateral drive axis while the drive or Coriolis mass is designed to be stiff in the sense axis. Designed orthogonal mode resonances for the drive and sense mass are 13 KHz and 154 KHz respectively. The drive-axis can be further stiffened orthogonally via constant force feedback using electrostatic control.

The total drive mass for this gyroscope assembly is computed as the sum of the sense mass plus the frame mass.

Fig 2. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) image of a previously fabricated optical accelerometer which is substantially similar to the gyro sense mass. This same process flow will be used to fabricate the optical gyroscope.

An analysis was performed to find the optimum sense-axis quality factor, Q_s , based on the number and size of the viscous damping holes shown in Fig 1. The analysis closely followed the work of

Ostergaard et al who considered a heat transfer analogy to solve for the squeeze film damping stiffness coefficients [3]. The results of the analysis are plotted in Fig 4 below as a function of the packaging pressure. For this design, a mechanical quality factor of 20,000 was chosen based on a package pressure of approximately 10 mTorr.

Fig 4. Effect on mechanical quality factor, Q, as the package pressure is varied between 0.1 mTorr and 100 Torr. For this design a Q of 20,000 was chosen.

III. ANALYSIS

This section analyzes the gyroscope design in terms of the optical response of the resonant cavity, mechanical mode analysis and noise sources contained within the system.

A. Optical Cavity

For simplicity, the Fabry-Perot cavity can be modeled as an ideal cavity where both upper and lower mirrors have identical reflectivities and are optically flat and parallel to one another. In this case, the photo-generated current, I_{ph} , collected by the transmission of light through the cavity can be modeled as

$$I_{ph} = \frac{-RP_0}{1+F\sin^2\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}ny(a)\right)} \quad (2)$$

where R is the responsivity of the diode in (A/W), P_0 is the incident optical power on the cavity in (W), F is the reflection Finesse and related to the mirror

reflectivity, λ is the wavelength of the incident light in (m) and $y(a)$ is the Coriolis acceleration dependent displacement of the sense mass in (m). While (1) provides useful insight into the operation of the Fabry-Perot cavity a full dielectric matrix solution must be used for the more general case where both mirrors are not identical and mirror curvature exists [4].

Using (2), for analytical simplicity, the change in optical transmission with a changing optical cavity length can be calculated as

$$T_r \sim \frac{dI_{ph}}{dy} = \frac{4\pi RFP_0 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}ny(a)\right) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}ny(a)\right) n}{\left(1+F\sin^2\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}ny(a)\right)\right)^2} \frac{1}{\lambda} \quad (3)$$

The ideal operating point, i.e. bias point, on the optical transduction curve can be found by solving for the local maximum of the derivative of (3). For a low Finesse cavity the optimum bias point is roughly $\lambda/8$ from either a local maximum or local minimum in the transduction curve corresponding to maximum constructive or maximum destructive interference respectively. A higher Finesse will result in a larger transduction value and therefore increased sensitivity to mechanical displacement but will simultaneously result in a reduced dynamic range if operated open-loop or present a tougher problem for the control electronics in a force feedback system.

B. Gyro Mechanics

The mechanics of the gyroscope are based on the use of Coriolis rotational force felt by a mass at velocity as given by equation (4) and illustrated in Fig 5.

$$F_y = -2m(v_x \times \Omega_z) \quad (4)$$

Fig 5. Diagram illustrating the Coriolis force in action.

The dynamics of the gyroscope can be described for both the lateral “drive” and vertical “sense” by (5-7) and (8-10) respectively [5].

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + \frac{\omega_x}{Q_x} \frac{dx}{dt} + \omega_x^2 = \frac{F_{comb}}{m_d} \sin(\omega_x t) \quad (5)$$

$$x(t) = \frac{Q_x F_{comb}}{m_d \omega_x^2} \sin\left(\omega_x t + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) = \frac{Q_x F_{comb}}{m_d \omega_x^2} \cos(\omega_x t) \quad (6)$$

$$v_x(t) = -\frac{Q_x F_{comb}}{m_d \omega_x} \sin(\omega_x t) \quad (7)$$

Vertical “Sense” Dynamics:

$$F_{coriolis} = -2m_d \Omega_z v_x(t) = \frac{2\Omega_z Q_x F_{comb}}{\omega_x} \sin(\omega_x t) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{d^2y}{dt^2} + \frac{\omega_y}{Q_y} \frac{dy}{dt} + \omega_y^2 = \frac{F_{coriolis}}{m_s} = \frac{2\Omega_z Q_x F_{comb}}{m_s \omega_x} \sin(\omega_x t) \quad (9)$$

$$y(t) = \frac{2Q_x Q_y \Omega_z F_{comb}}{m_s \omega_x^2 \omega_y} \sin(\omega_x t + \phi_y) \quad (10)$$

Where

$$\Delta\omega_{xy} = \omega_x - \omega_y \quad (11)$$

$$Q_y' = \frac{Q_y}{\sqrt{1 + Q_y^2 (\Delta\omega_{xy})^2 \left(\frac{\omega_x + \omega_y}{\omega_x \omega_y}\right)^2}} \quad (12)$$

$$\phi_y = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{Q_y \Delta\omega_{xy}} \left(\frac{\omega_x \omega_y}{\omega_x + \omega_y}\right) \right] \quad (13)$$

From (10) it can be shown that the sense-axis displacement sensitivity as a function of rotation is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{y_0}{\Omega_z} &= 2 \frac{Q_x F_{comb}}{\omega_x^2} \frac{Q_y'}{\omega_y} \frac{1}{m_s} = \\ &= 2 \frac{Q_x F_{comb}}{m_d \omega_x^2} \frac{Q_y'}{\omega_y} \frac{m_d}{m_s} = 2x_0 \frac{Q_y'}{\omega_y} \frac{m_d}{m_s} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

From (14) it can be seen that the sense-axis displacement is not only related to the force induced by the comb drive actuation and hence velocity but also the ratio of drive mass to sense mass. The design presented in Fig 1 and 2 takes a dual mass approach in an attempt to decouple drive and sense-axis and therefore take advantage of the additional multiplication in sensitivity by the ratio of the two

masses. For the gyroscope design considered here with sense and drive masses of 2.6e-7 Kg and 4.3e-6 Kg respectively along with drive and sense axis Q of 20,000 and resonant frequencies of 10,590 Hz and 10,480 Hz respectively results in a mechanical displacement sensitivity of 2.4e-9 m/(°/s).

To determine the output current or voltage from the sensor as a function of the rotational rate it is necessary to determine the internal Scale Factor (SF) of the optical transducer. Because the transducer inherently produces a photo-generated current with a changing input rotational rate, i.e. Coriolis force, the internal scale factor of the sensor is in units of amps per unit displacement (A/m). The scale factor of the sensor, (15), is calculated as the average steady state bias current at the nominal operating point times the transmission coefficient at the nominal operating point. Alternatively, the scale factor can be calculated in volts per unit of displacement (V/m) if the input impedance of the amplifier is taken into consideration. In (16), R is the input impedance to the transimpedance amplifier.

$$SF_I = I_{PD} \Delta T_r \quad (15)$$

$$SF_V = R I_{PD} \Delta T_r \quad (16)$$

An optimum resistance can be found based on the Johnson noise of the resistor and the current noise of the optical detector. The current noise of the sensor photo-detector is the sum total noise comprised of laser noise, Brownian motion noise of the proof mass and shot noise of the photo-detector itself. If the current noise is converted to an equivalent voltage noise by multiplying by the transimpedance resistance, R , and then set equal to the resistive Johnson noise itself once can solve directly for the optimum resistance and hence gain of the amplifier given by equation (18).

$$V_{noise} = I_{noise} R = \sqrt{4k_B T R \Delta f} \quad (17)$$

$$R = \frac{4k_B T \Delta f}{I_{noise}^2} \quad (18)$$

To express the scale factor as amps per rotational rate (A/°/s) or volts per rotational rate (V/°/s) it is necessary to take (15) and (16) and multiply by the

mechanical sensitivity of the device as given by (14) resulting in (19) and (20) respectively.

$$\frac{dI}{d\Omega_z} = SF_I \frac{y_0}{\Omega_z} = I_{PD} \Delta T_r 2x_0 \frac{Q'_y m_d}{\omega_y m_s} \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{dV}{d\Omega_z} = SF_V \frac{y_0}{\Omega_z} = RI_{PD} \Delta T_r 2x_0 \frac{Q'_y m_d}{\omega_y m_s} \quad (20)$$

The full scale rotational range of the sensor, FS , is determined by the full scale voltage of the electronics, FS_V , divided by the voltage scale factor of the sensor.

$$FS = \frac{FS_V}{dV/d\Omega_z} = \frac{FS_V}{RI_{PD} \Delta T_r 2x_0 \frac{Q'_y m_d}{\omega_y m_s}} \quad (21)$$

The minimum detectable displacement of the sensor, Δy_{min} , is calculated by dividing the total system voltage noise by the voltage scale factor of the device, (16).

$$\Delta y_{min} = \frac{V_{noise}}{SF_V} = \frac{V_{noise}}{RI_{PD} \Delta T_r 2x_0 \frac{Q'_y m_d}{\omega_y m_s}} \quad (22)$$

C. Noise Sources

Six different noise sources are considered in the following analysis: 1) Brownian motion, 2) wavelength drift, 3) Optical Relative Intensity Noise (RIN), 4) photodiode shot noise, 5) electronic noise, and 6) Resistive noise. All noise sources produce an equivalent rotational rate. The frequency content of the noise sources dictates the short-term and long-term stability of the sensor.

1) Brownian Motion

Brownian motion noise is a fundamental limiting noise source that impacts the final rotational resolution of the sensor. The displacement of the proof mass to Brownian motion is a function of the spring constant of the sensor and the damping coefficient which is turn in a function of packaging pressure, temperature, quality factor of the mechanical sensor and viscous damping.

$$\Delta y_{Brownian} = \frac{\sqrt{4k_B T D_s}}{k_s} \quad (23)$$

The input referred rotational noise due to Brownian motion can be expressed in several different ways. The simplest form is to take the displacement induced Brownian motion noise and equate that to an equivalent rotational rate.

$$\Delta \Omega_{Brownian} = \frac{\Delta y_{Brownian}}{2x_0 \frac{Q'_y m_d}{\omega_y m_s}} = \frac{\sqrt{4k_B T D_s}}{2x_0 \frac{Q'_y m_d}{\omega_y m_s}} \quad (24)$$

2) Wavelength Variation

Optical wavelength variation with temperature is simply the measured linear shift in wavelength with temperature times the change in temperature, ΔT_s , given by (25).

$$\Delta \lambda_{temp_s} = \frac{d\lambda}{dT} \Delta T_s \quad (25)$$

There are two fundamental sources that result in a voltage change due to a shift in wavelength. The first is the change in wavelength with temperature described by (25). The second is the change in wavelength with optical drive current. The change in wavelength with optical drive current is another linear parameter that can be measured and is typically less than 0.1 nm/mA. Total voltage induced wavelength drift can be expressed as Root Sum Square (RSS) of the two different noise contributors

$$\Delta V_{\Delta \lambda} = SF_V \left(\Delta \lambda_{temp_s}^2 + \Delta \lambda_{current}^2 \right)^{1/2} = RI_{PD} \Delta T_r \left(\Delta \lambda_{temp_s}^2 + \Delta \lambda_{current}^2 \right)^{1/2} \quad (26)$$

where

$$\Delta \lambda_{current} = \frac{d\lambda}{dI_{drive}} \frac{P_{Laser}}{10^{dB/20}} \frac{1}{\eta} \quad (27)$$

The change in voltage with wavelength can now be related to an equivalent rotational rate stability by dividing (26) with the output change in voltage with rotational rate, (20).

$$\Omega_{\Delta \lambda} = \frac{\Delta V_{\Delta \lambda}}{dV/d\Omega_z} = \frac{RI_{PD} \Delta T_r \left(\Delta \lambda_{temp_s}^2 + \Delta \lambda_{current}^2 \right)^{1/2}}{RI_{PD} \Delta T_r 2x_0 \frac{Q'_y m_d}{\omega_y m_s}} \quad (28)$$

It should be noted that (28) results in units of °/sec and not °/sec/√Hz. Actual noise density will therefore depend on the time-dependent wavelength drift.

3) Optical RIN

Noise due to Laser Relative Intensity Noise (RIN) can be shown to be equal to

$$\Omega_{RIN} = \frac{1}{2x_0 \frac{Q_y m_d}{\omega_y m_s}} \frac{1}{10^{\frac{RIN}{20}}} \quad (29)$$

4) Shot noise

Input referred acceleration due to shot noise can be shown to be equal to

$$\Omega_{shot} = \frac{\sqrt{2qI_{avr}}}{dI/d\Omega_z} = \frac{\sqrt{2qI_{avr}}}{I_{PD}\Delta T_r 2x_0 \frac{Q_y m_d}{\omega_y m_s}} \quad (30)$$

5) Electronic Noise

The input referred rotational rate induced by the electronics_noise floor is given by

$$\Omega_{electronics} = \frac{V_{Noise_electronics}}{R I_{PD}\Delta T_r 2x_0 \frac{Q_y m_d}{\omega_y m_s}} \quad (31)$$

6) Resistive Noise

Resistive Noise can be shown to be equal to

$$\Omega_{resistive} = \frac{\sqrt{4k_B T R}}{R I_{PD}\Delta T_r 2x_0 \frac{Q_y m_d}{\omega_y m_s}} \quad (32)$$

The final composite system noise can then be calculated at the Root Sum Square (RSS) of all the noise sources or

$$\Omega_{TOTAL} = (\Omega_{resistive}^2 + \Omega_{electronics}^2 + \Omega_{shot}^2 + \Omega_{RIN}^2 + \Omega_{\lambda}^2 + \Omega_{Brownian}^2)^{1/2} \quad (33)$$

An overall error budget was calculated using the equations presented above to determine total Angle Random Walk (ARW) of the system. For the calculations the following values were assumed: input optical power of 1 mW, wavelength of 850 nm, wavelength drift of 0.06 nm/°C a sense mass of 2.6e-7 kg, drive mass of 4.3e-6 kg, resonant drive frequency of 10,480 Hz, resonant sense frequency of 10,588 Hz, and a Q for both the sense and drive axis of 20,000. The results are presented in Table I.

Table I. Summary table with noise contributions from the various noise sources.

Summary		
Noise Source	Value	Units
Electronics	7.56E-07	(deg/s)/rHz
Brownian Motion	4.72E-08	(deg/s)/rHz
Laser SNR	2.32E-05	(deg/s)/rHz
PD Shot Noise	2.05E-06	(deg/s)/rHz
Wavelength Deviation	9.71E-07	(deg/s)/rHz
Resistive Noise	3.68E-07	(deg/s)/rHz
	2.34E-05	(deg/s)/rHz
	1.40E-03	deg/rHr

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A novel gyroscope design incorporating an electrostatic drive mechanism and an optical transducer has been presented. The design is substantially similar to previous optical accelerometers thereby allowing the potential integration of accelerometers and gyroscopes on the same silicon wafer. Due to the low noise optical transducer, decoupling of drive and sense electrodes, and the large mass ratio between sense and drive we have calculated an overall noise floor of 0.0014 °/√hr. This design will be fabricated and tested during the next fiscal year.

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